

Appendices for Real-world news coverage of disruptive environmental protest has mostly positive and strikingly uniform effects

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This document contains the full hypotheses, methods and results for the paper “How 100 news articles about disruptive protest affect environmental attitudes”. Unless indicated, all content is fully in accordance with the preregistration for this paper, which can be found on [OSF](#). Section [J](#) lists deviations (all minor) from the preregistration, and they are also noted in the text where relevant.

Further technical documentation can be found in the paper’s Technical Materials (Anon 2026). These include (1) details on article sampling, screening, summarising, and checking; (2) a full list of the prompts used in LLM pipelines; (3) results of ex ante power analyses; and (4) reports on two pilot studies. The pilots were used to select article/protest features (based on which ones which were reasonably common and possible to measure reliably) as well as to fine-tune the hand-coding instructions for them.

A Hypotheses

The first research question is about the effect of a *typical* disruptive climate protest on the salience of climate change, climate change concern, support for climate policy, behavioural intentions, and identification with environmentalism (H1–5). We hypothesize that exposure to a representative sample of articles about disruptive climate protest will on average:

- H1. increase the salience of climate change;
- H2. increase concern about climate change;
- H3. increase support for climate change policy;
- H4. increase intentions to take climate-related collective action;
- H5. decrease identification with environmentalism.

The salience of climate change captures how much it is at the top of people’s minds as a societal problem. Increasing climate salience through media attention is a typical stated goal of (disruptive) climate protest organisers, in order to put pressure on politicians. Indeed, public preferences are more likely to be reflected in policy outcomes when the issues at stake are highly salient (Giger and Lefkofridi 2014; Lax and Phillips 2012; Rasmussen, Reher, and Toshkov 2019).

Next, we look at concern about climate change—a common way of measuring general engagement with the issue (Bergquist et al. 2025). We also measure support for climate policy and intentions to take collective action. These are perhaps the most politically relevant aspect of environmental attitudes, given that public support is the most important predictor of climate policy adoption (Yeganeh, McCoy, and Schenk 2020). Likewise, collective action has been argued to be “the most efficient method of achieving emission reductions” (Roser-Renouf et al. 2014, p. 163; see also Schmitt et al. 2020).

We also measure environmentalist identity, since it is proposed that de-identification from the movement and its issues is the main mechanism behind potential opinion backlash (Feinberg, Willer, and Kovacheff 2020; Kenward 2024; Simpson, Willer, and Feinberg 2022; Bashir et al. 2013). The idea is that when respondents learn about protest actions that they see as extreme, they will conclude that environmentalists are “unlike them”, and perhaps move their attitudes and behaviours away from those associated with environmentalism. We thus hypothesize that identification mediates the effects on other attitudes, where effects via decreased identification are negative (H6), but effects on those attitudes via other pathways (the direct pathway in our analysis) are positive (H7, see main text Methods section on mediation for a discussion of causal identification in meditation analyses).

The second question is about the effect of protest and article features on attitudes. In order to limit the number of statistical comparisons, we create one compound environmental attitude index containing all outcomes except salience and identity. We hypothesise that the effect of disruptive protest articles on environmental attitudes depends on:

H8. the number of protesters;

H9–12. the level of disruption caused to businesses, the public, government, and culture/sports;

H13–16. whether blockades, attaching/climbing, event interruptions, or vandalism-like tactics are used;

H17. the tone of the article;

H18–20. the amount of words the article spends on the protesters’ message, on the disruption, and on negative comments;

H21. the total perceived amount of disruption caused;

H22. whether the protesters come across as ordinary people;

H23. whether the form of protest is judged to be acceptable.

The protest and article features whose impacts we chose to evaluate are based on a combination of theory and existing findings.¹ Large numbers could lend legitimacy to the protesters’ demands and cause others to jump on the bandwagon (Tilly 1995; Schmitt-Beck 2015)—though Wouters (2013) does not find evidence for this. The targets and tactics chosen for a disruptive protest

1. We originally included an additional hypothesis, predicting an effect of whether the protesters’ messaging is also about non-environmental issues. Such issue bundling could also hamper persuasion by alienating people who do not agree with the protesters on those issues (Marshall et al. 2024). After analyzing the features of our set of 100 articles, but before collecting experimental data, we concluded that almost no articles reported on any non-environmental issue bundling. In accordance with our pre-registration, we dropped this hypothesis, as it could not be tested with our data.

are known to change its perceived appropriateness (Badullovich et al. 2024), which could in turn drive persuasion or backlash. The tone of the portrayal of protesters and the space given to criticism are a straightforward case of framing effects, as the media outlet and commenters are suggesting to the reader how to feel about the protest (McLeod and Detenber 1999; McLeod and Hertog 1992).

If attention is given to the message, protesters not only have more opportunities to verbally persuade the reader—they are also given legitimacy (Brown and Mourão 2021). Attention to the disruption, on the other hand, can be delegitimizing (id.). Protests that are perceived as very disruptive, and protesters who come across as very different from ordinary people, may also be especially likely to trigger de-identification from their cause (Feinberg, Willer, and Kovacheff 2020; Simpson, Willer, and Feinberg 2022). Finally, the perceived acceptability of a protest can be seen as the final product of all these factors. It may seem obvious that a protest seen as less acceptable will have more negative outcomes. However, given the number of studies that find no difference between the effect of disruptive and non-disruptive protests on attitudes towards the cause (Brehm and Gruhl 2024; Bugden 2020; Fuller et al. 2025; Gonzatti, Hunger, and Hutter 2023; Vandeweerd 2025), this is worth investigating further.

B Article screening: criteria and validation

Here, we describe the criteria that an article should meet in order to be filtered into the population of disruption articles. This is the population from which the final sample of treatment articles are selected (at random but weighted by the outlet’s readership). There are both content eligibility criteria and format criteria. Next, we describe the steps we took to validate the performance of the LLM (Claude Sonnet) in screening the articles by these criteria.² Note that these processes in particular are described in detail in the Technical Materials (Anon 2026).

We use the shorthand “disruptive climate protests” to refer to the types of protests we are interested in, because all disruptive environmental protest we identified during the test period foregrounded climate, but our definitions (including in LLM prompts) refer to environmental protest more generally. Although such articles are rare, there is at least one article included in our 100 articles about specific environmental protests that has no climate focus (it concerns disruption of a whaling ship).

B.1 Content criteria

We evaluate the content eligibility for each article in two steps:

1. The article must first meet the broader criterion: the answer must be yes to the question “In a counterfactual world identical to ours, except that

2. Piloting and validation was done using Claude Sonnet 3.5; article processing for the final study was done using Claude Sonnet 4.0.

environmental protesters never used disruptive methods, would this article still exist in a form where the primary message was hardly changed?” This criterion is assessed by Claude. We support this step by doing quality control of the final selected sample of treatment articles, flagging and swapping out any articles that do not in fact meet this criterion. Use of LLM facilitates our workflow despite the necessity for manual checking of screened in articles because we do not manually assess automatically screened out articles. The Technical Materials (Anon 2026) contain a full description of the screening workflow.

2. The article must then meet a narrower criterion: “The article’s main focus is on one disruptive environmental protest, or a small number of such protests all closely linked in theme, time and protest method. This means that in a counterfactual world identical to ours, except that this protest (or these protests) had not occurred, the article would not exist in a form where the primary message was hardly changed.”

The reason why we filter in two steps, rather than going directly to the narrow criterion in step 2, is because articles that pass step 1 but not step 2 are used in an additional analysis. This analysis is described in the main text (see section “Effect of all articles owing their existence to disruptive protests”). It is aimed at assessing the public opinion effects of disruptive protests more comprehensively.

B.2 Format criteria

In order to end up in the treatment population, the article must also be judged by Claude to pass the following format checks:

1. It may not consist of one or more readers’ letters to the editor. Letters tend to be short and include no headline or pictures. Debate articles, which tend to be longer and have those elements, were allowed to be included on the other hand.
2. It may not be a “news roundup”, i.e. a collection of short updates or links to other articles. These updates are often thematically related but the article as a whole is not a coherent single article of the type that would appear in a print edition.
3. It may not be in a language other than English (e.g., Welsh articles from the BBC) or clearly originate from a non-UK edition of the news outlet (for example, the Guardian and the Daily Mail both have Australian editions).
4. It may not be centred almost exclusively around one or more videos, meaning there is no text in the article that is not video caption (serving the purpose of explaining the video).

In the quality control step, we flagged and swapped out any such articles that were incorrectly filtered in by Claude.

B.3 Screening validation

To validate the LLM’s performance in applying filtering criteria, before pre-registering we compared LLM and human research assistant (RA) coding for the primary coding criterion (Step 1) for 50 randomly selected articles (confusion matrix in Table B.1). As with all analyses conducted before pre-registering, this analysis was conducted on articles drawn from a two-year pilot period preceding the actual article sampling period. This way, we avoided extensively exposing ourselves to articles from the actual research period (see main text Methods subsection “Selecting disruptive climate protest articles — Article search”).

Table B.1: Confusion Matrix for Human vs. LLM Screening Criterion Step 1 Coding

Article passes human screening	Article passes LLM screening	
	No	Yes
No	22	2
Yes	1	25

The main quantity of interest here is recall; that is, the percentage of true positives (articles that meet the criterion according to a human) that are caught as positives by the LLM (i.e. are indeed screened in). Recall is satisfactory at 96% (25 out of 26), implying that only 4% (1 out of 26) of the articles that should have been in our stimulus pool were incorrectly filtered out.

The precision of the model—the rate at which the articles it filters in are true positives rather than false positives—is 93%. This means that among the filtered-in articles, 7% should not have been in the stimulus pool. This aspect of performance is less relevant, because we manually evaluate each filtered-in article, deleting it from the stimulus sample if we judge it to be a false positive. Deleted articles are replaced by another randomly selected article from the same outlet.

When applying this method to obtain our final sample of 100 articles, we did not re-evaluate recall as this would have involved manual coding of a large number of screened-out articles, but precision was 92%.

C LLM article summary validation

If the original article is longer than 350 words, we ask Claude to summarise it down to 300. Before pre-registering this LLM-based summarization procedure, we validated it to make sure article content was not changed in any important ways. Our validation starts from the list of features that we believe might have an impact on attitudes (see subsection “Protest and article features” in the main text, Method section). These include features of both the protest and its presentation in the article. The validation procedure shows us whether the summarisation process preserves the distribution of features. This is key in order

to preserve the representativeness (external validity) of our average treatment effect. If the summarization systematically changed the ratings in a particular direction (e.g. making the tone more neutral despite our prompt instructions to preserve the tone), it may introduce bias that would skew the average treatment effect in a particular direction.

We asked a research assistant to first code the (quality-controlled, human-edited) summaries of a randomly selected subset of 50 articles on all features that are to be rated by RAs in the final study—namely, all objective features of the protest plus the article’s tone in portraying the protest (see Appendix D).³ Four months later, we asked the research assistant to rate the full-length version of the articles. We then compared average ratings on the features between the full-length and summarised versions, focusing our analysis on the 43 articles that had indeed required summarization. With respect to the article’s tone of portrayal, the bias is likely to take the form of articles having a less clear tone (whether negative or positive). For that reason, we also investigate a version of the variable that is “folded” in the middle (i.e. turning the five-point scale into neutral tone, mild tone, strong tone). This way, we can see whether the intensity of the tone decreased.

Table C.1 shows the average ratings for the full-length and summarised articles, and tests their difference using Bayes factors. In all cases except one, the Bayes factors provide weak to moderate evidence that summarization made no difference (a larger sample might have provided stronger evidence). The exception is the presence of Alterations/Vandalism as a form of disruption, meaning that activists temporarily or permanently altered a physical structure (e.g. spray-painting a building), where there was weak evidence for a difference. There were five articles that the RA rated as containing this type of disruption in their original version, while they had coded the summarised version as not containing it.

In four of these cases, the original article was a broader portrayal of a movement or a specific activist, but the summarised version focused on a single protest, leaving out a brief mention of a different protest that involved alterations or vandalism. In fact, these original articles did not meet our criterion of being due to a specific protest (see Appendix B, section Content criteria). Instead, they should have been set aside for the separate analysis that also included such broader, non-protest-specific articles (see Methods section, Effect of all articles owing their existence to disruptive protests). This highlights an issue with our article pipeline as we originally piloted it, where human quality check of the inclusion criteria happened after rather than before summarization. Re-filtering all 43 articles in this validation analysis, we found a total of six non-protest-specific articles. Table C.2 shows the result of the validation when those articles are left out. With this set-up, the evidence points in the direction of no difference for all features.

3. We include Issue bundling although it was dropped from the study (see Footnote 1) in compliance with a pre-registered decision rule, because it was too rarely present to be analysed. However, we include it here to demonstrate that its rareness is not due to such messaging being dropped in the summarization process.

Table C.1: Results of summarization validation

	Mean, sum- mary	Mean, origi- nal	Diffe- rence	Bayes Factor
No. of protesters	3.88	4.08	0.19	0.31
Disruption to targets				
General public	2.53	2.33	-0.21	0.90
Environmentally damaging businesses	1.63	1.79	0.16	0.31
Disruption to authorities	1.33	1.26	-0.07	0.19
A cultural or sporting event or institution	1.42	1.49	0.07	0.18
Disruption tactics				
Blockade	0.81	0.79	-0.02	0.18
Attaching/Climbing	0.58	0.56	-0.02	0.19
Alterations/Vandalism	0.21	0.33	0.12	1.93
Interrupting an event	0.16	0.09	-0.07	0.69
Issue bundling	1.12	1.14	0.02	0.17
Tone of portrayal	3.07	2.84	-0.23	0.62
Tone of portrayal, folded	0.77	0.77	0.00	0.16

Note. Comparing mean ratings for summarised and original articles by the same RA. Bayes Factor interpretation: $.10 < BF < .33$ is moderate evidence for no difference; $.33 < BF < 1$ is weak evidence for no difference; $1 < BF < 3$ is weak evidence for a difference.

Table C.2: Results of summarization validation, articles about specific protests only

	Mean, sum- mary	Mean, origi- nal	Diffe- rence	Bayes Factor
No. of protesters	3.79	4.08	0.29	0.83
Disruption to targets				
General public	2.46	2.27	-0.19	0.60
Environmentally damaging businesses	1.65	1.73	0.08	0.20
Disruption to authorities	1.24	1.22	-0.03	0.18
A cultural or sporting event or institution	1.43	1.43	0.00	0.18
Disruption tactics				
Blockade	0.81	0.76	-0.05	0.28
Attaching/Climbing	0.51	0.49	-0.03	0.21
Alterations/Vandalism	0.24	0.27	0.03	0.28
Interrupting an event	0.16	0.08	-0.08	0.74
Issue bundling	1.14	1.16	0.03	0.19
Tone of portrayal	3.00	2.81	-0.19	0.37
Tone of portrayal, folded	0.70	0.73	0.03	0.18

Note. Comparing mean ratings for summarised and original articles by the same RA. Bayes Factor interpretation: $.10 < BF < .33$ is moderate evidence for no difference; $.33 < BF < 1$ is weak evidence for no difference.

D Article feature coding

Each news article stimulus must be rated on a number of features that might influence its effect on environmental attitudes. We subdivide these features into “objective” traits, which were rated by two RAs; traits that are encoded in the count of words in the article dedicated to different aspects (e.g. consequences of the disruption), which were rated by LLM (as described in detail in Technical Materials, Anon 2026); and “subjective” traits, which were rated by a panel of 14 crowd-coders for each article.

Table D.1 below contains the wordings of the questions that we asked of the RAs, LLM and crowd coders. Each crowd-coder had 15 minutes to code five summarised articles (pilot studies showed that this timing is reasonable). For features marked with an †, coders were given the opportunity to indicate that the article does not contain enough information to form a judgment.⁴ If at least half of the coders judge this to be the case for a given feature of an article, then that feature of that article was considered missing.

The table also shows the intraclass correlation (ICC) between coders. An ICC of .9 is considered to signify excellent inter-rater reliability (Koo and Li 2016). The strong ICCs we report are due in part to an extensive piloting process. As a result of these pilots, we both fine-tuned coding instructions and discarded potential features with low inter-rater reliability. In case of the RA ratings, the high reliability is also due to careful training where RAs first jointly coded a set of randomly selected practice articles, to further tune instructions and synchronise our joint understanding of them. In all cases, we report the ICC for the *average* rating across coders, as that is what we use on our analyses. For the RA-coded features, we use the two-way mixed effects ICC model. For the crowd-sourced features, we use random effects of rater, because each article gets a random set of raters.⁵

An analysis of data from Badullovich et al. (2024) suggested that ideology is by far the most important driver of people’s opinions of disruptive protests, and that other demographics (age, gender, education) have little explanatory power when ideology is controlled for. We therefore ensured that (as far as possible) every article was read by a set of 14 coders that was balanced on ideology.

4. The pre-registration specifies that if they did so, their rating would not be used. We deviated from this by using the respondent’s rating anyway, as it was based on the same amount of information as the ratings from the respondents who felt more confident. This mirrors our pre-registered approach to RA ratings.

5. For the RA ratings, we only care that raters should be internally consistent, not that their scores should be correct in an absolute sense. That is because the same two raters scored all articles, so any bias due to the rater will affect all articles equally. For the crowd-sourced features, we do care about raters being correct in an absolute sense, since we do not want an article’s score to depend on the subset of raters that it happened to be assigned to. According to the Shrout and Fleiss (1979) convention, these ICC types are called ICC (3,k) and ICC (2,k) respectively.

Table D.1: Feature Coding Scheme and Reliability.

Feature (rated by)	ICC	Question
No. of protesters (RAs) †	.92	What is your best estimate of how many people are taking part in the protest? (8-point scale: 1, 2-3, 4-10, 11-30, 31-100, 101-300, 301-1000, More than 1000)
Disruption to targets (RAs)		How much disruption does the article describe as being caused by the protest to each of the following entities? (5-point scale from None at all to A great deal)
General public	.93	The general public going about everyday activities
Environmentally damaging businesses	.96	Business operations usually perceived as environmentally damaging
Authorities	.97	Government or local authority operations (not including police)
Culture/sport	.96	A cultural or sporting event or institution
Disruption tactics (RAs)		What types of disruption are mentioned as being part of the protest? (binary, multiple selections allowed)
Blockade	.94	Blockade
Attaching/ Climbing	.94	Protesters physically attached to or on top of something
Alterations/ Vandalism	.97	Temporary physical alterations or vandalism
Interruption	.93	Interrupting an event or speech
Tone of portrayal (RAs)	.88	Would you say that the article portrays the protest in a hostile, neutral or sympathetic way? (5-point scale from Very hostile to very sympathetic)
Article word counts (LLM)		Prompt asking LLM to tag all word sequences and pictures in the article that cover...

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Table D.1 – *Continued from previous page*

Feature (rated by)	ICC	Question
on message	-	... the messages protesters are trying to convey, for example quotes (from a person or a banner) or reported summaries of things protesters said.
on disruption	-	... general disruption effects (direct or knock-on) of the disruptive protest
on negative comments	-	... criticism of the protest or its effects. This might be expressed by a quoted individual, reported in general terms (e.g., ‘passers-by shouted disapprovingly’), or expressed by the author of the article.
Perceived overall disruption (Crowd)	.99	How much disruption would you say the protest caused? (5-point scale from None at all to A great deal)
Protesters seeming ordinary (Crowd)	.93	Besides being environmental activists, would you say the protesters come across like ordinary people? (5-point scale from Not at all to Very much like ordinary people)
Acceptability of protest (Crowd)	.98	Do you find this form of protest acceptable or unacceptable? (5-point scale from Very unacceptable to Very acceptable)

For the word counts (based on the LLM tagging phrases as relevant to the word count category, see Technical Materials, Anon 2026), we also take into account pictures that convey either the message of the protesters (e.g. a photo of a banner) or the disruptive effects of the protests (e.g. footage of queuing cars). These are a key way for news outlets to frame protests (Brown and Mourão 2021). We ask Claude to code whether each picture was about either of those aspects, and count a picture as being equivalent to 50 words. The median article in our final set after summarization contained 349 words and two pictures. All words and pictures in the article can in principle be assigned to more than one category at once. We take the natural logarithm of the picture-augmented word counts (plus one) before adding them to the model. We take the log both because we believe that extra words have decreasing marginal effects, and to limit the influence of outliers.

Figure D.1: Correlation matrix of article/protest features.

D.1 Feature intercorrelations

Figure D.1 shows the correlations between all pairs of features. Two pairs of features jump out as particularly highly correlated. Number of Protesters is correlated with the Tactic: blockade ($r=0.67$), following from the fact that more protesters are typically needed to establish a blockade than for the other tactics. And Disruption to: public has a surprisingly strong correlation with Public perception: protest disruptive ($r=0.75$). This indicates that when members of the public rate the disruptiveness of a protest, they base their judgement heavily on how much ordinary people were disrupted. Appendix section H.2 reports on pre-registered analyses that avoid controlling for one variable in these pairs while estimating the effect of the other. This is to investigate if any null effects might be due to lack of power in analyses that control for both (though results ultimately do not differ from the main analyses).

Besides these two strikingly strong correlations, other connections also stand out. Disruption to culture or sport tends to require fewer protesters, and so do protests using vandalism (including minor physical alterations). Vandalism as

a tactic does not tend to be used together with blockades or protesters attaching themselves to something—perhaps because the same physical target (e.g. building, road or bridge) rarely lends itself to both. Protests are seen as more acceptable if they use blockades, perhaps because blockades are more likely to be used to directly prevent climate-damaging activities. Not unsurprisingly, protests rated as more disruptive are also rated as less acceptable.

When trying to establish causal connections between these features and protests’ public opinion effects, we deal with these naturally occurring correlations between protest/article features by running two analyses. In the main text, we control for any features that we believe are causal precedents of the feature of interest (see main Methods subsection Effect by protest/article features). In a pre-registered alternative analysis, we investigate the bivariate connections between features and environmental attitudes, without controlling for any other features (see Appendix section I.3). The results of both analyses are substantively the same.

E Attitude and background variable measurement

Table E.1 documents the response scales and the sources of the items used to measure environmental attitudes in the survey experiment. All these outcome variables, except salience, also have a “don’t know” response option. In statistical modelling, “don’t know” is replaced with the value at the mid-point of the bipolar response scale. This is reasonable because in all cases the mid-point represents an absence of a relevant opinion. Recall that to analyse the effects of article features (and mediation of the articles’ pooled main effect by environmentalist identity), we combine all Concern, Support and Behavioural intention items into a scale. The scale has a Cronbach’s alpha of .89 (based on wave 1 measurements).

Table E.2 shows the background variables we collect, and their response options. For all variables except one, we used items that had been previously validated and/or previously used in disruptive protest research. The exception is policy support; here, we chose policy items that had been previously fielded (but not formally validated) by two opinion-tracking organizations. We selected these on the basis that they were impactful climate policies that had also been controversial among respondents, making them unlikely to produce ceiling effects.

Table E.1: Environmental Attitude Measurement Details.

Outcome	Response scale	Notes
Salience	Coded as 1 if respondent mentions “climate”, “biodiversity”, “pollution”, “environment”, “nature”, or “warming”	Standard “most important problem” item; used as an outcome of disruptive protest by Vandeweerd (2025).
Climate change concern	Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Somewhat disagree (3), Neither agree nor disagree (4), Somewhat agree (5), Agree (6), Strongly agree (7)	From Kenward and Brick 2024.
Climate policy support	Strongly Oppose (1), Oppose (2), Somewhat oppose (3), Neither support nor oppose (4), Somewhat support (5), Support (6), Strongly support (7)	From Akehurst (2024, based on YouGov surveys) and Climate Barometer Tracker (2025)
Behaviour intention	Very unlikely (1), Unlikely (2), Somewhat unlikely (3), Neither likely nor unlikely (4), Somewhat likely (5), Likely (6), Very likely (7)	From the participatory actions subscale of the validated Environmental Action Scale by Alisat and Riemer (2015), updated by Oinonen and Paloniemi (2023) to reflect new online tools.
Environmental identity	Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Somewhat disagree (3), Neither agree nor disagree (4), Somewhat agree (5), Agree (6), Strongly agree (7)	From Brick and Lai (2018).

Table E.2: Background Variable Measurement Details.

Variable	Response scale	Notes
Sex	Male, Female	Provided by Prolific
Age	In years	Provided by Prolific
Education	No formal qualifications (1), Secondary education (e.g. GED/GCSE) (2), High school diploma/A-levels (3), Technical/community college (4), Undergraduate degree (BA/BSc/other) (5), Graduate degree (MA/MSc/MPhil/other) (6), Doctorate degree (PhD/other) (7)	Based on Prolific’s scale but measured in wave 1 survey
Ideology	Very left-wing (1), Fairly left-wing (2), Slightly Left-of-centre (3), Centre, (4) Slightly right-of-centre (5), Fairly Right-wing (6), Very right-wing (7), Don’t know (99)	From Newman et al. (2024)

F Respondent sampling and representativeness

F.1 Sampling strategy

We recruited 3788 UK residents on Prolific to fill out wave 1 of our study between from November 14th and November 26th 2025. Next, we re-contacted respondents to invite them to participate in wave 2 of the study, which included the experiment. All participants were re-invited between 10 and 14 days after participating in wave 1, and were given a week to complete wave 2. We sent several reminders, and payment for both waves was conditional on completing them both. 3479 respondents (92%) participated in wave 2. Among those, we randomly assigned 257 respondents to an additional data collection on the effects of news articles owing their existence to disruptive protest, but not covering a single protest (see main paper Methods section “Effect of all articles owing their existence to disruptive protests”). The other 3222 respondents participated in our primary experiment.

As much as possible, we aimed for our sample to be representative of the UK adult population with respect to ideology, age and binary sex. Because Prolific does not have enough active UK participants in total to create a fully representative sample of this size, we prioritised representativeness on ideology. We made this decision based on an analysis of data from Badullovich et al. (2024), which showed that ideology is the strongest predictor by far of people’s opinions of disruptive protests, and that age and gender have little explanatory power when ideology is taken into account. In practice, this meant that when wave 1 recruitment for a given demographic cell had become very slow or had stopped before the cell was filled up, we first blended sampling cells by sex (meaning people of any sex could fill the now-combined cell if they had the right age and ideology). If recruitment became very slow again, we allowed in respondents of adjacent ages; for example, recruitment for the cell of right-wing respondents aged 65+ was eventually expanded to allow respondents to be 55+ years old instead. Finally, for the cell of respondents aged 65+ who responded to an ideology self-placement question with “Don’t know”, we had to bring in respondents who self-identified as have a “Centre” ideology instead to fill the cell.

These measures, in addition to the fact that our successful re-contact rate was high but not perfect, meant that respondents were not perfectly representative. The section on Representativeness below compares our final sample’s demographics to the UK adult population.

F.2 Representativeness

Table F.1 compares the distribution of our wave 2 respondents’ ideologies, age and sex to the distribution in the UK adult population. Sex and age proportions come from mid-2024 UK census data (Office for National Statistics 2025). Ideology baseline data comes from a YouGov (2025) survey with a sample of 2038 UK residents, itself weighted to be representative of the UK population. YouGov’s respondents indicated their ideology on a seven-point scale from “Very

left-wing” to “Very right-wing” (with a “Don’t Know” option). Prolific only allows researchers to recruit UK respondents by their answer to a three-point ideology scale (“Left”, “Centre”, “Right”, plus “Don’t know”). To get a baseline for these categories, we collapsed YouGov’s question into three categories as well. We merged “Very left-wing”, “Fairly left-wing” and “Slightly left-of-centre” respondents, did the same for the three right-wing categories, and kept “Centre” and “Don’t know”. Prolific respondents were asked about their ideology between zero and six months before completing the survey, and YouGov’s data were collected in late March 2025, about eight months before we fielded wave 1. The collection time of our survey data and YouGov’s data was thus reasonably similar, especially given the slow-moving nature of population-level ideology.⁶

Demographic	Pct. in survey	Pct. in population	Difference
Left	30.4	29.0	1.4
Centre	27.4	22.0	5.4
Right	26.2	26.0	0.2
DK	16.1	22.0	-5.9
18-24	7.9	10.5	-2.6
25-49	44.2	41.3	2.9
50-64	30.9	24.2	6.7
65 plus	17.0	23.9	-6.9
Female	56.2	51.6	4.6
Male	43.8	48.4	-4.6

Table F.1: Comparing proportions of respondents in demographic categories to UK population statistics (source: YouGov and Office for National Statistics).

Overall, the representativeness of the sample is imperfect but reasonable. The sample somewhat over-represents ideological Centre respondents at the cost of respondents with ideology “Don’t know”. Age groups 25-49 and 50-64 are overrepresented slightly, but since their extra respondents come from the age groups below and above them, respectively, the average age of our sample (48) is reasonably close to the average age of the adult population (54). Female respondents are slightly overrepresented. These relatively minor deviations from representativeness are mostly due to decisions on our part to fill demographic cells with respondents of another sex, adjacent ages, and as a last resort, Centre rather than “Don’t know” ideology. Appendix I.1 shows the results of re-weighting the sample to be fully representative.

6. For example, an analysis of replication data from Dassonneville (2021) shows that when we take the average ideology of UK residents on a 10-point scale, the median year-over-year change in this number between 2010 and 2017 was just 0.01.

G Models

All responses complete for both waves are included in the analyses. Below, we provide pseudo-code and details for each of the models used in our analyses. Full analysis code is available in the Technical Materials (Anon 2026).

G.1 Effect of a typical news article

In this analysis, we estimate one model per attitudinal outcome. Written in pseudo-R code, and making use of the package `lmerTest`, this model is:

```
lmer(outcome_wave2 ~ treated + outcome_wave1 +  
      (-1 + treated | article), data=d)
```

The quantity of interest is the coefficient of `treated`. As is typical practice within the stimulus sampling approach, we use random factors to model the uncertainty coming from the fact that the stimuli are a sample of, rather than the full population of, all possible stimuli representing our treatment concept (Judd, Westfall, and Kenny 2012; McNeish, Stapleton, and Silverman 2017). Since we compare 100 treatment stimuli to one control group, we do this by including random effects of articles in the model, but only for treated respondents (coded here as a random slope of the treatment effect by article, but no random intercept).

In an alternative analysis, we weight observations by the likelihood of their article outlet–ideology combination. We use the survey package in R to take these weights into account.⁷ Because the package does not allow for including random effects, we dropped the random effects of article for this analysis (see section H.1.3 for results that confirm this is unproblematic). The model is:

```
design <- svydesign(ids = ~1, weights = ideo_outlet_weight,  
                  data = data)  
svyglm(outcome_wave2 ~ treated + outcome_wave1, design = design)
```

where `ideo_outlet_weight` is the probability that the tested combination of respondent–ideology and article would occur in the real world, based on the Reuters Digital News Report survey (Newman et al. 2024). These probabilities are adjusted to make up for the fact that popular sources are already over-represented in the sample (otherwise, we would be doubly overweighting the most-read outlets). We do this by dividing the probabilities by the proportion

7. Note that in the pre-registration, we planned to use the package `WeMix` for this analysis, because it allows for the inclusion of random effects as well as survey design weights. However, we were unaware that the package (1) is unable to handle our random term structure (random slopes of treatment, no random intercept) and (2) can only calculate cluster-robust standard errors (CR-0). Based on simulations, we concluded that CR-0 standard errors are likely not appropriate. In our case they are also far smaller than non-robust standard errors; this would make it challenging to compare the uncertainty of the weighted analysis results to that of the main analysis. Effect size estimates from `WeMix` are identical to those from the survey package, however.

of articles in the sample that came from the source.⁸ Control respondents are weighted by the probability that someone with their ideology would read the outlets we include, averaged across outlets (giving more weight to more popular outlets). These probabilities are corrected for double-weighting in the same way.

To make this analysis possible, Wave 1 of our survey experiment includes the same seven-point ideology scale as the Reuters survey. However, we collapse the two most extreme categories on either side. This is because in the Reuters study, there are not enough respondents in the most extreme ideological categories to accurately estimate their news consumption habits.

Finally, we perform an analysis to investigate whether the effect of the treatment on attitudes is mediated by its effect on environmentalist identity. We pool all attitudinal outcomes (except salience and identity) into a compound environmental attitude scale (by taking the mean of z-transformed variables), and then estimate both the identity-mediated and the direct effect of the treatment on that scale.

To do so, we start by taking the first difference (Wave 2 minus Wave 1 values) for both the mediator (identity) and the outcome (attitude scale), so we can test whether a change in identity due to the treatment mediates a change in the outcome. See Analyses subsection Mediation by environmentalist identity in the main text for a discussion of why this strategy helps with identification of the mediation effect.

Next, we regress change in the mediator on the treatment variable; we regress change in the outcome on the treatment and change in the mediator; and finally we use the mediation package in R to use the estimates from these models to compute mediation effects. The pseudo-code is:⁹

```
fit_MtoT <- glmer(identity_change ~ treated +
  (- 1 + treated | article), data=d)

fit_YtoM <- glmer(outcome_scale_change ~ treated + identity_change +
  (- 1 + treated | article), data=d)

mediate(fit_MtoT, fit_YtoM, sims=50, treat="treated",
  mediator="identity_change")
```

The effect sizes of interest are (1) the average mediated causal effect of protests on attitudes via environmentalist identity, and (2) the direct effect of the protests when identity is held constant, a.k.a. the direct natural effect (Imai et al., 2011).

8. We did not mention this correction in the pre-registration, as we had not realized there was a need for it.

9. In our preregistration, we mistakenly included clustering by article in the mediation model code (`cluster=article`); this is unnecessary because of the presence of random effects, and a mediation model requiring both will not run. Moreover, due to an implementation issue with random effects in the mediation package, the modelling function had to be changed from `lmer()` to `glmer()`. This is inconsequential; the model continues to be a linear random-effects model.

G.2 Effect by article features

Here, we once again pool all outcomes (except salience and identity) into a compound scale. We then run four models, in which we progressively add variables, block by block (see Analyses in main Methods section for an explanation). We use only treated respondents, looking at the effect of features that vary across articles. So, for instance, the first model is:

```
lmer(outcome_scale_wave2 ~ numberOfProtesters + ... + tactic_interrupt  
+ outcome_scale_wave1 + (1 | article), data=d[d$treated,])
```

Where ... stands for the other features in the first block (objective protest features).

The final model includes all listed features from all blocks:

```
lmer(outcome_scale_wave2 ~ numberOfProtesters + ... + acceptability  
+ outcome_scale_wave1 + (1 | article), data=d[d$treated,])
```

Where ... stands for the other features in all blocks.

The quantities of interest are the coefficients on the features of the block that was just added to the model. These coefficients show how climate change attitudes among treated respondents vary depending on each feature of the protest or article, assuming the causal relationships between features that are shown in Figure 1 (main text). Note that in these cases, adding random effects of articles can be done more straightforwardly with an article-level intercept, as we do not have the issue of control group respondents having no such random effects.

Three features (Number of Protesters, Perceived Overall Disruption and Protesters Seeming Ordinary) were allowed to have missing values if most of the coders judged that there was not enough detail in the article to rate the feature (see section D). In practice, this was the case for three articles with respect to number of protesters, and two articles with respect to seeming ordinary. Still, we want to avoid dropping those articles from the analyses entirely. Instead, we impute the median value for that feature in that article. We also add a dummy variable to the analysis, which equals 1 when a respondent saw an article whose value on that feature was imputed. This keeps the features' imputed values from interfering with their estimated effect.

This approach is plausibly unbiased for cases where the missing value is actually undefined (Allison 2010)—as opposed to a respondent e.g. forgetting or declining to fill out a survey item. That is most likely the case for our missing values. When most raters found a feature to be unratable for an article—for example, when asked to rate the number of participants at a protest that had been announced but had not taken place yet—then that article simply has no value for that feature.

G.3 Multiple testing correction

Besides presenting the raw p-values, we also show p-values corrected for multiple testing. They are calculated using the adaptive two-stage approach from Benjamini, Krieger, and Yekutieli (2006), which controls the false discovery rate (FDR). The FDR is the rate at which discoveries (null hypothesis rejections) can be expected to be false. By setting the FDR to .05 we ensure that out of all confirmed hypotheses, the expected rate of false positives is no more than 5%. The approach adjusts p-values so that the FDR is indeed limited at .05.

We apply the approach separately to our two research questions, about (1) the average effect of exposure to an article on different environmental attitudes (H1-7), and (2) the effect of protest/article features (H8-23). In other words, we control the FDR for the hypotheses about the effect of reading a disruptive protest article on various environmental attitudes, and separately for the hypotheses about the effect of various protest features on the aggregated environmental attitude scale. Since these are conceptually different questions, which speak to different theories and readers, we believe this is more meaningful than controlling for the FDR of all hypotheses combined. Our answer to question (1) should not be influenced by how many features we decided to test for question (2), and vice versa for the number of attitudes tested in question (1).

We present both unadjusted and adjusted p-values because limiting the FDR has the obvious downside that it decreases power to detect true positives. Practitioners may care just as much about a false negative (e.g. we incorrectly conclude that the target of the disruption does not matter for public opinion) as a false positive (e.g. we incorrectly conclude that it does). The number of other tests run would not change this logic. We present the unadjusted p-values so that it remains possible to evaluate the evidence for each hypothesis separately, regardless of which others were tested.

H Full pre-registered analysis results

H.1 Effect of a typical news article

H.1.1 Treated and control group means

We start by showing the raw means for every outcome in the treated and control group, pre-treatment (wave 1) and post-treatment (wave 2) in Table H.1. We also show the trend (pre-post difference) in both groups, and the difference in those trends. These differences in trends are not exactly identical to our treatment effect estimates below, because wave 1 outcomes are not subtracted from wave 2 outcomes in our model. Instead, wave 1 outcomes are used as controls. n is slightly below 3222 for some outcomes because in rare cases, respondents were successfully re-contacted but did not complete wave 2 in its entirety. In these cases, we use the outcomes that they did fill out, but drop the respondent from the analyses of the outcomes that they did not fill out. All

outcomes are on their original scales: binary (0–1) for Salience, and a seven-point scale for the other outcomes.

	Control			Treated			Diff-in-diff	
	Pre	Post	Diff.	Pre	Post	Diff.	DiD	n
Salience	0.15	0.17	0.01	0.13	0.28	0.15	0.13	3222
Concern	4.93	4.92	-0.01	5.01	4.95	-0.06	-0.05	3222
Policy	3.91	3.90	-0.01	3.99	4.07	0.07	0.09	3218
Intentions	3.38	3.25	-0.13	3.50	3.33	-0.17	-0.04	3216
Envir. identity	4.34	4.35	0.01	4.43	4.13	-0.30	-0.31	3222

Table H.1: Pre- and post-treatment means for the control and treated groups, pre-to-post differences for both groups, and finally the difference between those differences, on the original outcome scales.

H.1.2 Regression results: treatment effects

Table H.2 shows the treatment effect and its standard error, p-value, 95% confidence interval, and FDR-corrected p-value for each outcome, without standardization. Salience (mentioning climate or the environment as a top three issue) is binary; the other outcomes are on seven-point scales.

Outcome	Est.	SE	p	CI, min	CI, max	p (FDR)
Salience	0.13	0.02	0.000	0.09	0.16	0.000
Concern	-0.04	0.04	0.218	-0.11	0.03	0.163
Policy	0.09	0.04	0.008	0.02	0.17	0.008
Intentions	-0.02	0.04	0.636	-0.09	0.06	0.381
Envir. identity	-0.29	0.04	0.000	-0.38	-0.21	0.000

Table H.2: Main effect of article treatment on environmental attitudes, unstandardized.

Table H.3 shows the same information, but with all outcomes standardised. We standardised outcome variables by dividing them by their standard deviation in wave 1. While less interpretable (in particular for the binary outcome of Salience), these results make it possible to compare effect sizes between the outcomes. These standardised results are represented in Figure 2 in the main paper.

All models control for the respondent’s environmental attitude outcome as measured in wave 1. n per outcome for all these analyses can be found above in Table H.1.

Outcome	Est.	SE	p	CI, min	CI, max	p (FDR)
Salience	0.38	0.05	0.000	0.28	0.48	0.000
Concern	-0.03	0.02	0.218	-0.07	0.02	0.163
Policy	0.06	0.02	0.008	0.02	0.10	0.008
Intentions	-0.01	0.03	0.636	-0.06	0.04	0.381
Envir. identity	-0.18	0.03	0.000	-0.23	-0.13	0.000

Table H.3: Main effect of article treatment on environmental attitudes, standardized.

H.1.3 Weighting by source and ideology

In an alternative analysis, we weight treated respondents by the likelihood that someone with their ideology would actually read the outlet they were exposed to as their treatment (see main paper Methods section Alternative analysis: weighting by source and ideology). Figure H.1 shows these likelihoods, using polling data from Newman et al. (2024). The two most extreme values are collapsed on either side of the seven-point ideology scale, because the most extreme values on their own do not capture enough respondents to get a reasonable estimate of outlet reading likelihoods. As the figure illustrates, not all sources have skewed readership; some attract readers evenly across the ideological spectrum. As a result of that, most respondent–outlet combinations in our study do not receive extreme weights (interquartile range: 0.80–1.10).

Table H.4 documents the treatment effect of the articles with this weighting applied, using standardised outcomes. Results are very similar to the unweighted analysis results in Table H.3. As explained in section G.1, in this analysis, we were unable to include random effects of article. We judge this to be unproblematic, because the random effects in our main analysis have extremely small variance (0.028 for Salience, < 0.0025 for other outcomes, with outcomes standardised), meaning they explain hardly any variability in environmental attitudes. Moreover, when we repeat our main analyses without random effects, results are essentially unchanged (treatment effect estimates differ by no more than 0.0003, and SEs differ by no more than 0.0004, with outcomes standardised).

H.1.4 Heterogeneous treatment effects by ideology

Table H.5 shows the interaction effects between the article treatment and respondents’ ideology on a seven-point scale (excluding respondents with “Don’t know” responses). Negative effects indicate that for every additional point to the right a respondent finds themselves on the ideological spectrum, the treatment affects them more negatively. Because such interaction effects can be difficult to interpret, Figure H.2 presents the conditional effect of the treatment, depending on the respondent’s ideology. As the figure shows, articles about disruptive protest raise the salience of climate change/the environment

Figure H.1: Probability of reading each outlet, given ideology self-placement from “Very/Fairly left-wing” (1–2) to “Very/Fairly right-wing” (6–7), or “Don’t know” (DK).

Outcome	Est.	SE	p	CI, min	CI, max	p (FDR)
Salience	0.39	0.04	0.000	0.31	0.48	0.000
Concern	-0.03	0.02	0.164	-0.07	0.01	0.123
Policy	0.05	0.02	0.014	0.01	0.10	0.014
Intentions	-0.01	0.03	0.809	-0.06	0.05	0.485
Envir. identity	-0.19	0.02	0.000	-0.24	-0.14	0.000

Table H.4: Main effect of article treatment on environmental attitudes, standardized. Responses are weighted by the likelihood of a respondent reading the outlet of their treatment article, given their ideology.

for everyone, but less so for right-wing respondents. Similarly, they lower environmentalist identity for everyone, but less so for left-wing respondents (this difference is marginally significant). For Concern and Intentions, on the other hand, the effects on left- and right-wing respondents have different directions. It is worth noting again that with the exception of Salience, all effect sizes are small, and that the most extreme left and right ideological categories are rarely used (resp. 5% and 2% in our sample).

Outcome	Est.	SE	p	CI, min	CI, max	p (FDR)
Saliency	-0.07	0.03	0.028	-0.14	-0.01	0.028
Concern	-0.03	0.01	0.021	-0.06	-0.00	0.028
Policy	-0.00	0.01	0.968	-0.03	0.03	0.581
Intentions	-0.04	0.02	0.017	-0.08	-0.01	0.028
Envir. identity	-0.03	0.02	0.080	-0.07	0.00	0.060

Table H.5: Interaction effect between ideology (7-pt. scale from “Very left-wing” to “Very right-wing”) and article treatment on environmental attitudes, standardized.

Figure H.2: Effect of disruption article treatments on (standardised) environmental attitudes, conditional on respondent’s ideology (7-pt. left-to-right scale). Zones are 95% confidence intervals.

This analysis suggests that for climate concern and behavioural intentions, disruptive climate protest could be slightly polarizing, increasing the gap between left-wing and right-wing people in the UK on climate and the environment. In Appendix section I.2, we explore this further by checking whether the treatment effect also depends on previous environmental attitudes. For each attitude, we check whether participants who already had more pro-environmental attitudes pre-treatment also respond more positively to the treatment. In contrast to what we might have expected based on these ideology interaction findings, we find no evidence for any such polarizing effects.

H.2 Effect by article features

Table H.6 shows the coefficient of each protest/article feature and its standard error, p-value, 95% confidence interval, and FDR-corrected p-value. The out-

come is a standardised compound environmental attitude scale (composed of Concern, Policy support and Behavioural intentions—see main text Methods section on Outcomes). This scale has a standard deviation of 1. In this table, features are unstandardised, as measured on their original scales. Number of Protesters is on an eight-point scale, levels of disruption to targets are on a five-point scale, tactics are binary (present or not), portrayal is on a five-point scale, words are logged word counts (plus one to avoid taking the log of zero), and public perceptions are on five-point scales (see main Methods section Protest and article features). Models control for features that are in the same or earlier causal blocks as the examined feature (see main Methods section Effect by protest/article features).

Feature	Est.	SE	p	CI	FDR
Number of Protesters	0.00	0.01	0.703	-0.01 – 0.02	0.866
Disruption to: polluting business	0.01	0.01	0.638	-0.02 – 0.03	0.866
Disruption to: public	-0.01	0.01	0.161	-0.03 – 0.00	0.638
Disruption to: authority	-0.02	0.02	0.251	-0.06 – 0.01	0.638
Disruption to: culture/sport	-0.01	0.01	0.689	-0.03 – 0.02	0.866
Tactic: blockade	0.00	0.03	0.947	-0.06 – 0.06	0.947
Tactic: attachment	0.01	0.03	0.790	-0.04 – 0.05	0.903
Tactic: vandalism (often minor)	0.02	0.03	0.552	-0.04 – 0.07	0.866
Tactic: event interruption	-0.01	0.03	0.868	-0.07 – 0.06	0.926
Article: positive portrayal	0.02	0.02	0.114	-0.00 – 0.05	0.638
Article: words on disruption	-0.03	0.01	0.029	-0.06 – -0.01	0.461
Article: words on protester message	-0.01	0.01	0.200	-0.02 – 0.00	0.638
Article: words negative about protest	0.00	0.00	0.509	-0.01 – 0.01	0.866
Public perception: protest disruptive	-0.03	0.02	0.229	-0.07 – 0.01	0.638
Public perception: protesters ordinary	0.01	0.02	0.639	-0.03 – 0.05	0.866
Public perception: protest acceptable	0.03	0.03	0.279	-0.02 – 0.08	0.638

Table H.6: Effect of features (unstandardized) on environmental attitudes.

Next, Table H.7 shows the protest/article feature analyses with standardised features (i.e. each of them rescaled to set their standard deviations to 1). As is the case for the standardised outcomes in the section above, standardization makes individual effect sizes more difficult to interpret (especially for binary features), but makes them easier to compare to one another. That is why the standardised feature results are used in Figure 3 in the main paper. $n = 2573$ for all these analyses, as they use treated respondents only.

Our article/protest feature rating process showed that two pairs of features were highly correlated with one another. This was the case for the number of protesters and the disruption tactic of enacting a blockade ($r = .67$); and for disruption targeting the public and public perceptions of the disruptiveness of the protest ($r = .75$). For that reason, we pre-registered additional analyses where these pairs of variables were not included in the model at the same time. We report analyses using standardised feature variables. Feature effects were

still small and non-significant, and similar to those from the main analyses:

- the effect of Number of protests in a model without Tactic: blockade (.01, $SE = .01$, $p = .637$, FDR-corr. $p = .865$);
- the effect of Tactic: blockade in a model without Number of protests (.00, $SE = .01$, $p = .754$, FDR-corr. $p = .906$) and
- the effect of Public perception: protest disruptive in a model without Disruption to: public ($-.02$, $SE = .01$, $p = .077$, FDR-corr. $p = .155$).¹⁰

Feature	Est.	SE	p	CI	FDR
Number of Protesters	0.01	0.01	0.703	-0.02 – 0.03	0.866
Disruption to: polluting business	0.01	0.01	0.638	-0.02 – 0.03	0.866
Disruption to: public	-0.02	0.01	0.161	-0.04 – 0.01	0.638
Disruption to: authority	-0.01	0.01	0.251	-0.03 – 0.01	0.638
Disruption to: culture/sport	-0.01	0.01	0.689	-0.03 – 0.02	0.866
Tactic: blockade	0.00	0.01	0.947	-0.03 – 0.03	0.947
Tactic: attachment	0.00	0.01	0.790	-0.02 – 0.03	0.903
Tactic: vandalism (often minor)	0.01	0.01	0.552	-0.02 – 0.04	0.866
Tactic: event interruption	-0.00	0.01	0.868	-0.02 – 0.02	0.926
Article: positive portrayal	0.02	0.01	0.114	-0.00 – 0.04	0.638
Article: words on disruption	-0.02	0.01	0.029	-0.04 – -0.00	0.461
Article: words on protester message	-0.01	0.01	0.200	-0.03 – 0.01	0.638
Article: words negative about protest	0.01	0.01	0.509	-0.01 – 0.02	0.866
Public perception: protest disruptive	-0.02	0.02	0.229	-0.05 – 0.01	0.638
Public perception: protesters ordinary	0.00	0.01	0.639	-0.01 – 0.02	0.866
Public perception: protest acceptable	0.02	0.02	0.279	-0.01 – 0.05	0.638

Table H.7: Effect of features (standardized) on environmental attitudes.

In the Alternative analyses section below, we report on analyses where the relevant environmental attitudes are not combined into a scale (section I.3) and analyses where no other features are controlled for when testing the effect of one feature (section I.4).

H.3 Effect of all articles owing their existence to disruptive protests

Finally, we present the results of the analysis including ten additional articles, which owe their existence to disruptive climate protests without being about one specific protest (or a few very similar protests). We only run the analyses for the main effect of the pooled article treatments. Analysing features would

10. Our main analyses already do not control for Public perception: protest disruptive when estimating the effect of Disruption to: public, as we considered the former to be a possible consequence of the latter; see main Methods section Effect by protest/article features.

not be meaningful here: as these additional analyses do not cover one protest, it does not make sense to ask, for instance, how many protesters were present.

Table H.8 shows the treatment effect and its standard error, p-value, 95% confidence interval, and FDR-corrected p-value for each standardised outcome. $n = 3479$ to 3472 depending on outcome. Comparison with Table H.3, which shows the effect of only specific-protest articles on standardised outcomes, shows us that results are nearly identical.

Outcome	Est.	SE	p	CI, min	CI, max	p (FDR)
Salience	0.38	0.05	0.000	0.28	0.48	0.000
Concern	-0.02	0.02	0.273	-0.06	0.02	0.205
Policy	0.06	0.02	0.009	0.01	0.10	0.009
Intentions	-0.01	0.03	0.678	-0.06	0.04	0.407
Envir. identity	-0.19	0.03	0.000	-0.24	-0.13	0.000

Table H.8: Main effect of article treatment on environmental attitudes, standardized. Includes respondents seeing ten additional articles not covering a specific disruptive protest.

I Alternative analyses

This section contains non-preregistered analyses that investigate whether our main analysis results hold under different specifications. We report on analyses where respondents are weighted to adjust for small deviations from representativeness on demographics. We then investigate whether the treatment is polarizing, by checking interactions between the treatment and previous environmental attitudes. We also estimate the effect of each protest/article feature without controlling for others, and we check the effect of protest/article feature on different types of environmental attitude outcomes.

I.1 Analyses re-weighted for full representativeness

Figures I.1 and I.2 show our analyses of the article treatment effect and of the article/protest feature effects, re-weighted so that the sample is fully representative of the UK population on the joint distribution of ideology, (binned) age and sex. As Appendix section F.2 shows, the main differences between our sample and the population are an under-representation of respondents who are 65 plus years old, and respondents who have a “Don’t know” ideology response. We used the R package survey to implement survey design weighting. This means random effects had to be left out of the model, but we judge this to be unproblematic, because random effects in the main analyses explained negligible variability (cf. Appendix section H.1.3). The joint probabilities of ideology, age and sex were raked given the joint distributions of ideology by age, ideology by

sex, and age by sex (Office for National Statistics 2025; YouGov 2025).¹¹

Figure I.1: Main effect of article treatment on environmental attitudes, standardised. Responses are weighted to representative of the UK population on ideology, age and sex.

Comparing Figure I.1 to the unweighted results with standardised outcomes in main text Figure 2, we see that effect sizes are very similar, though the positive effects on Salience and Policy are slightly smaller. The Policy effect also falls below the threshold of statistical significance, due to the greater uncertainty introduced by the weights. Comparing Figure I.2 to the unweighted results with standardised features in main text Figure 3, confidence intervals are slightly wider but conclusions are the same: no features have meaningful effects. Words spent on disruption still have a small effect that is statistically significant, but is rendered insignificant when multiple testing correction is applied.

While valuable, we believe that there are a few potential reasons why these results are somewhat less reliable than those of our main analyses. To calculate weights, we had to bin ages into bands of variable width (determined by YouGov), and YouGov’s seven-point ideology measure, which we used to calculate population distributions, had to be binned into three categories. Moreover, the time of data collection does not correspond perfectly between YouGov’s baseline/population data and our survey. In addition, ideology question wording was not identical (Prolific wording read “Where do you sit on the political spectrum?” and its “Don’t know” options were labeled “N/A” and “Prefer not to say”). This matters, because small differences in ideology scale wording have been shown to have important effects in Europe (McRoy and Pancratz 2020).

11. In reality, the YouGov 2025 data specify the distribution of ideology by gender. However, as less than 1% of the UK population has a gender identity that is different from their sex assigned at birth Office for National Statistics (2023), we used these numbers as a close proxy for the ideology by sex distribution.

Figure I.2: Effect of features (standardised) on environmental attitudes. Responses are weighted to representative of the UK population on ideology, age and sex.

I.2 Polarisation: heterogeneous treatment effects by previous attitudes

Table I.1 investigates polarizing effects of the treatment. It shows the interaction effects between the treatment and each environmental attitude, measured pre-treatment. The outcome in each case is the same environmental attitude, measured post-treatment. A positive effect would indicate that people with higher values on the attitude scale were also more positively influenced by the treatment. This would result in polarization.

In reality, the only statistically significant effect we see is on environmentalist identity, and it is negative (though not significant after multiple testing correction). This means that people who more strongly identified as environmentalists before the treatment may have been especially likely to be *negatively* influenced by the treatment. This is surprising, as all environmental attitudes have a negative correlation with left-to-right ideology (e.g. $r = -0.32$ between pre-treatment environmentalist identity and ideology). Since we found clear heterogeneous treatment effects by ideology on most attitudes (see section H.1.4), we might have expected the same to be true for pre-treatment environmental attitudes. In sum, this analysis does not suggest that the treatment was polarizing.

I.3 Bivariate article feature analyses

Figure I.3 shows the effect of (standardised) features on the compound environmental attitude scale without controlling for any other features. This is the equivalent of Figure 3 in the main paper, but estimating one model per

Outcome/moderator	Est.	SE	p	CI, min	CI, max	p (FDR)
Saliency	0.07	0.05	0.120	-0.02	0.16	0.301
Concern	-0.01	0.02	0.766	-0.05	0.03	0.766
Policy	0.01	0.02	0.563	-0.03	0.06	0.766
Intentions	-0.01	0.03	0.683	-0.06	0.04	0.766
Envir. identity	-0.06	0.03	0.036	-0.11	-0.00	0.180

Table I.1: Interaction effects between the article treatment and pre-treatment environmental attitudes. Outcome is the same attitude post-treatment. Positive effects indicate polarization. All attitudes standardized.

feature. We only control for the respondent’s pre-treatment attitudes. The outcome is a compound scale of environmental attitudes (concern, policy support and behaviour). As the main paper Methods section explains (see Effect by protest/article features), we did not register this as the main analysis because it risks turning up spurious correlations—for example, blockade tactics might seem effective at changing opinions, but the reason might be that protests using this tactic also tend to have more protesters present.

As it turns out, however, most features continue to have null effects. Confidence intervals are even narrower than in the main analysis, staying between $[-0.04, 0.04]$ for all features. Two features related to the disruptive effects of the protest have statistically significant effects: the words spent on disruption in the article, and public perception of the protest of disruptive. Public perception of the protest as acceptable also has a statistically significant effect. However, all three effect sizes are extremely small (all -0.02 on the standardised outcome scale, all $SE = .01$, $p = .008$ and 0.039 and $.043$). No effects are statistically significant after applying multiple testing correction (all $p > .12$).

I.4 Article feature effects on each attitude type

In this analysis, we investigate the effect of protest/article features on each type of environmental attitude (Concern, Policy support and Behavioural intentions) rather than combining all three outcomes into a compound scale. We do this in case the features affect different attitudes in different ways. Figure I.4 shows the results of this analysis. All outcomes are standardised. Conclusions are in line with the main analyses: very small effects with narrow confidence intervals.

A few effects are statistically significant before multiple testing correction: a positive effect of disruption to businesses on Concern (0.03 , $SE = 0.01$, $p = .033$), a negative effect of words in the article about disruption on Policy support (-0.02 , $SE = 0.01$, $p = .049$), a positive effect on more sympathetic portrayals of the protesters on Behavioural intentions (0.03 , $SE = 0.01$, $p = 0.049$) and a negative effect of words about the protesters’ message on Behavioural intentions (-0.03 , $SE = 0.01$, $p = 0.021$). As one might expect, all effects are non-significant after we apply multiple testing correction to these 48 comparisons

Figure I.3: Effect of protest/article features on environmental attitudes (outcome and all features standardised), with 95% confidence intervals without multiple testing correction. Each feature analyzed in a separate model without controlling for others. See main paper Design overview section for an explanation of the “causal block” color coding.

(all $p > .5$). Because of this, and because none of these outcome-specific effects of features connect clearly to theory, we find it likely that these are false positive results. Regardless, the effect sizes are extremely small.

Figure I.4: Effect of protest/article features on different environmental attitudes (outcomes and all features standardised), with 95% confidence intervals without multiple testing correction.

J Deviations from the pre-registration

Our implementation of the experimental design and analysis deviated from the [pre-registration](#) in the following (minor) ways:

- Our articles were sampled from the period going two years back from September 30th, 2025, but no articles were sampled from the first week (i.e. the sampling period only started on October 8th 2023).
- We did not preregister to exclude "articles" which were in fact pages embedding podcasts, but did so in one case (see Technical Materials, Anon

2026).

- We conducted more detailed additional manual checks and corrections of the article summary process than preregistered (see Technical Materials, Anon 2026).
- We did not drop ratings from crowd-coders who said they were unsure about their score for a particular article on a particular feature. We reasoned that if the majority of raters were fairly sure about their rating, then everyone’s ratings were based on sufficient information and should be taken into account. An article feature was coded missing, however, if a majority of coders said they were unsure (as pre-registered). This means our approach to crowd-sourced ratings now exactly mirrors our approach to the ratings by research assistants.
- In the analysis where we weight responses by the likelihood of the combination of respondent ideology and treatment article news outlet, we made a correction to the way we calculated weights. The pre-registration described weights as “the probability that a respondent with this ideology would read this outlet”, but using those probabilities directly would result in a double overweighting of popular sources (as the most-read sources would be read more by respondents of all ideologies, but they were also already overrepresented in our sample of 100 treatments). We corrected for this by dividing weights by the number of respondents that were treated with the corresponding outlet.
- For this same analysis, we used the R package `survey` instead of `WeMix` to take weights into account. We did so because `WeMix` is only able to calculate standard errors (and therefore confidence intervals and p-values) that include are cluster-robust (type CR-0). This robustness correction unexpectedly shrunk standard errors by a factor of two to three, which we believe is likely incorrect (based on simulations to estimate true sampling variability), and which makes comparison to the main analyses difficult. The `survey` package is unable to fit random effects models, so we fit a model without article random effects instead. We judge this to be acceptable because the variance of our article random effects in the main analyses was near-zero, and because leaving out the random effects in that analysis led to near-identical results. The `survey` and `WeMix` approaches produced the same treatment effect estimates.
- The original preregistration included a minor mistake in the pseudocode for the model for mediation by environmentalist identity. Namely, it included clustering by article (`cluster=article`). This was not intentional, as we do not judge clustering to be necessary on top of the random effects. Moreover, the package cannot run the code as provided, as it cannot combine clustering with random effects. We therefore left out the clustering element in our analysis code.

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